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D3.2 Behavioral insights for improving research integrity

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Abstract

This document considers efforts to enhance research integrity from a behavior change perspective. This perspective involves identifying the causes of undesirable behaviors and ways to shape these in an ethical and effective manner. To facilitate this way of thinking, we identify four broad strategies that can influence problematic research behaviors by targeting four broad categories of causes of these behaviors: shaping competencies, shaping incentives, shaping communities, and shaping opportunities (CICO). We use this framework to integrate existing literature on both the causes and proposed remedies of questionable research practices as well as research misconduct.

According to the CICO framework, research integrity can be first facilitated by **shaping competencies** because research conduct depends in part on relevant knowledge, skills, and habits. For instance, improving research integrity training as well as equipping researchers to engage in self-regulation are promising ways to maintain integrity.

Second, research integrity can be facilitated by **shaping incentives** because research conduct depends in part on the expected consequences of actions, both in terms external rewards and punishments as well as in terms of internal alignment with psychological goals, values, and identities. For instance, pre-registration and registered reports reshape incentives by disentangling publication likelihood from the content of findings. Reminding researchers of their integrity values might increase the weight of these internal incentives on choices.

Third, research integrity can be facilitated by **shaping communities** because research conduct depends in part on the perceived behavior of pioneers, leaders, and majorities. For instance, the open science movement has sought to elevate the status of researchers who adhere to integrity principles and reduce the status of those who do not.

Finally, research integrity can be facilitated by **shaping opportunities** because research conduct depends in part on which actions are made easier to consider and implement by the structure of situations. For instance, various defaults, reminders, feedback, and self-reflection prompts could be incorporated into research software or pre-registration and publication portals.

These four strategies can be combined to form comprehensive interventions. Conduct of research is a complex behavior consisting of numerous decision points each with numerous action options. Such behaviors have many causes and therefore interventions targeting each one individually can have only a small effect. However, such small effects can accumulate over time and be combined to achieve larger results.

We also conducted an online experiment ($n = 634$) to test if an incentive shaping strategy of increasing the psychological salience of internal values or external adverse consequences would alter participants' evaluations and selection of low vs high integrity research behaviors in 10 vignettes from the Erasmus University Rotterdam's Dilemma Game. We found that the consequences manipulation and to a lesser extent the values manipulation indeed increased

preference for the high integrity option, but only in the first vignette where participants wrote about how the highlighted values or consequences applied to the situation described in the vignette. These results suggest that research integrity can be supported by interventions that induce researchers to think through, at the time of choosing between behavioral options, how the options at hand relate to specific adverse consequences that they wish to avoid and to specific personal values that they wish to live up to.

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List of Abbreviations

QRPs: Questionable research practices

RI: Research integrity

RM: Research misconduct

RCR: Responsible conduct of research

CICO: Competencies, Incentives, Communities, and Opportunities

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1 A framework for behavioral insights to facilitate research integrity

Research integrity is fundamental for ensuring scientific credibility and maintaining public trust in science, which is crucial for addressing societal challenges. In an era where parts of the world experience science skepticism or even outright denial by politicians and government officials, cultivating an ethical research culture becomes increasingly important to strengthen public confidence in scientific integrity (American Association for the Advancement of Science, 2025).

Research integrity manifests ultimately in behavior, in the actions that researchers take, fail to take, or refrain from taking. Adopting this behavioral perspective suggests that efforts to facilitate research integrity can draw insights from the scientific study of behavior change.

We use “research integrity” as a broad term that denotes the extent to which conduct of research adheres to different ethical norms. Integrity is a quality of research that can be undermined to different degrees both by questionable research practices (QRP) and by research misconduct (Fanelli, 2011). QRPs include a broad diversity of behaviors, which can be mostly understood as practices that lead to the omission or distortion of the information conveyed by any aspect of a study, in ways that may be more or less harmful depending on the context. Research misconduct (RM) is almost universally defined in terms of fabrication, falsification or plagiarism, which are actions that unequivocally distort the research literature.

The study of behavior change has a long history and has been particularly lively in the recent decades under the headings of nudging and behavioral insights (Benartzi et al., 2017). Behavior change research is interdisciplinary spanning anthropology, psychology, epidemiology, economics, sociology and other disciplines that help understand human behavior. This diversity is a source of strength but can also make it difficult to navigate the large body of concepts, frameworks, toolkits, and findings that have accumulated over the years (Hale et al., 2020; West et al., 2019). Here, we propose a simple umbrella framework to help experts of research integrity to think systematically about behavior change and start applying their domain knowledge to produce actionable behavioral insights.

1.1 The CICO framework

Assuming we have an ethically justifiable aim to change some aspects of someone’s behavior, we need to figure out how to achieve that aim in a cost-effective and ethical manner. A principled approach is to identify causes of the to-be-altered behavior that can be feasibly changed by ethical and effective means (Albarracín et al., 2024). For this purpose, our framework distinguishes four broad categories of causes of a behavior – competencies, incentives, communities, and opportunities (CICO). It then uses these categories to distinguish four broad behavior change strategies based on which causal category a strategy mainly seeks to change – shaping competencies, shaping incentives, shaping communities, and shaping opportunities.

For instance, suppose we want to reduce the known tendency of early career researchers to engage in QRPs (Xie et al., 2021). To do so, we can first use existing as well as original research

to identify potential causes of this behavior in the given target group from each of the CICO categories. As an example of *competencies*, early career researchers may lack sufficient knowledge to avoid some QRPs. As an example of an *incentive*, post-docs may feel intense competition towards tenure track jobs. As an example of a *community* aspect, graduate students may identify with the student community and its permissive norms towards academic cheating. As an example of an *opportunity*, early career researchers often work alone when analyzing data. Note that these are hypothetical examples, although some will turn out to be realistic based on the literature reviewed below.

Armed with a list of potential causes of a behavior, we can turn to identifying existing and novel interventions that could conceivably shape these causes in order to re-shape the behavior. For instance, we can *shape competencies* by conducting well-designed courses on research integrity (as recommended by the BEYOND project). We can *shape incentives* by requiring fewer fully published papers for PhD theses (as recently done in UK). We can *shape communities* by hiring graduate students as junior researchers to foster professional non-student identity (as recently done in Estonia). Or we can *shape opportunities* for QRPs by making statistical reviews a routine part of the peer review process (see for example Vazire, 2024 for an implementation at a prestigious journal). The identified interventions could then be ranked based on their expected effectiveness and feasibility, arriving at a short-list of ideas to be implemented, assessed, and if effective, scaled up.

Figure 1. The CICO framework of behavior change strategies

More formally, the four categories of behavioral causes can be defined as follows. The concepts apply to actions of interest - particular mental or physical actions of particular target groups. Often, the focus is on a pair of actions, one desirable and the other less so.

- **Competencies** are the knowledge, skills, habits, and traits of the actor that make an action of interest more or less likely.

- **Incentives** are the positive and negative outcomes that the actor expects an action of interest to deliver that make it more or less likely.
- **Communities** are significant groups and individuals whose perceived behavior and judgement make an action of interest more or less likely.
- **Opportunities** are aspects of situations where an action of interest occurs that makes it more or less likely.

Factors in each of these categories can become a primary target for intervention yielding the following four strategies.

- **Shaping competencies** involves developing the knowledge, skills, or habits that enable the desired relative to the undesired action.
- **Shaping incentives** involves altering the perceived or actual probability or value of expected outcomes of the desired or undesired actions.
- **Shaping communities** involves amplifying or dampening the social influence of leaders, pioneers, or silent majorities.
- **Shaping opportunities** involves making the desired action easier to consider and implement relative to the undesired action.

In the following four sections, we will consider each CICO component from three perspectives. **First**, we will use the four components to organize common themes in the literature on causes of research integrity. We hope to demonstrate how the framework can help make sense of disparate findings as well as to highlight potential under-investigated areas. **Second**, we will locate existing interventions within the framework as well as propose under-investigated intervention approaches. **Third**, we suggest brainstorming questions that could be used to facilitate intervention co-creation in various settings.

1.2 Competencies

Behavior depends in part on the competencies that a person brings to any situation. We often do not attempt things that we believe, correctly or incorrectly, we're not able to do well, or at all. For instance, a researcher is unlikely to adopt a new statistical practice such as equivalence testing instead of using absence of evidence as evidence of absence before they believe they know how to do it. We may also persist at things that come as second nature to us even if they are difficult or lonely. Think of the researchers who have mastered equivalence testing and use it, even though they occasionally need to do more work to convince reviewers of its merits. The competencies category includes knowledge and skills but also other relatively stable characteristics of individuals such as their personality traits and habits.

The literature on research integrity considers different competencies as key antecedents of research integrity. First, simply not knowing what is ethical can lead to unintentional violations. For instance, not understanding the interpretation of p -values well can lead to p -hacking. Likewise, an absence of skills can preclude researchers from adopting new practices. Beyond knowledge and skills, a few personality traits have been associated with research integrity. For instance, indicators of research misconduct correlate with consequentialist

ethical orientation (Fink et al., 2023), Machiavellianism (Tijdink et al., 2016), impatience, forgetfulness, and laziness (Davis et al., 2007). Some studies have also implicated male gender as a risk factor (Gopalakrishna et al., 2022).

1.2.1 Reshaping competencies

The sensitivity of research integrity to competencies opens the door for interventions that seek to re-shape behavior by shaping competencies. The idea of this strategy is to develop the knowledge, skills, and habits that enable the desired behavior. Competencies such as personality traits cannot usually be changed, but they could be taken into account to tailor interventions.

The competencies shaping strategy is perhaps the most common approach in the existing literature on research integrity interventions. Overall, research integrity training can be effective (Marušić, 2023). However, there are limits on the impact of knowledge. While courses of responsible conduct of research often succeed in increasing relevant knowledge, this need not translate into more ethical decision-making or attitudes (Powell et al., 2007). Some trainings have even been found to be harmful, reducing trainees' considerations of others and endorsing detrimental unethical behaviors (Antes et al., 2010). Based on a meta-analysis, successful training programs encourage active participation (e.g., debates, workbook exercises, etc.), are specific to the respective fields, and emphasize instruction through cases with low to moderate realism and emotional content (Watts et al., 2017). Other authors have further advocated for tailoring trainings to different disciplines; including research communication skills; combining formal and informal education formats; updating trainings regularly; and delivering them by qualified scientists (Labib et al., 2022). More broadly, authors advocate for a shift in research ethics and integrity education away from a focus on compliance with abstract principles towards approaches that emphasize reflexivity, contextualization, and sense-making using pedagogical techniques such as case study analysis and role-playing (Brummel et al., 2010; Labib et al., 2022). See deliverables of D6.1 and D6.2 of this project for more detailed consideration of educational interventions.

Competency shaping strategy can also involve empowering the individual to become the designer of their own behavior. Many forms of behavior change such as becoming more physically active involve deliberate self-regulation of behavior. Some questionable research practices such as selective analysis or p-hacking may be akin to unhealthy habits and thus sensitive to similar self-regulatory dynamics. Accordingly, long-term adherence to research integrity may benefit from researchers adopting an explicit goal to resist temptations and engage in strategies to meet that goal. Interventions aimed at supporting these efforts could target the factors that self-regulation is known to benefit from such a well-articulated sense of identity, effective metacognitive strategies, and a sense of personal agency (Frazier et al., 2021). Interventions may also provide self-regulatory skills such as reducing cues triggering bad habits in ones' workflow and making plans for generating new habits.

1.2.2 How to get started with reshaping competencies?

Applying the competencies shaping strategy requires identifying the knowledge, skills, and habits that could be shaped. Here are the questions that could be helpful in this process.

- *Knowledge*. Do people engaging in the desired action know or believe something that the ones engaging in the undesired actions do not? If so, how could we help people gain this knowledge?
- *Skills*. Are the skills that make the desired actions possible or easier? If so, how could we help people obtain these skills?
- *Habits*. Can behaving in the desirable way become habitual? If so, how could we support forming such habits?

Once the key competencies shaping the action of interest have been identified, we can proceed to find ways to shape them. The goal is to come up with interventions that would help people develop helpful knowledge, skills, and habits.

1.3 Incentives

Behavior is shaped by incentives, or the expected consequences of actions that we'd like to have more or less of. Although we're imperfect trackers of expected value, we tend to opt for actions that offer the best ratio of expected rewards to expected punishments. Think of figuring out which smartphone or laptop to buy by considering the advantages and disadvantages of different models.

Incentives therefore also shape the conduct of research. Each research decision can be thought of as a competition between available actions such as dropping vs keeping an analysis showing null results in a paper. Each action has some probability to produce various rewards and punishments. These can be *external consequences* such as getting the paper published. But they can also have *internal, psychological consequences* such as living up to the value of honesty or preventing emotions such as regret or shame. The perceived probability of these consequences can reflect their true probability but is often also somewhat biased. For instance, a consequence can seem more likely because it comes to mind more easily (i.e. has high salience), perhaps because it has been talked about a lot recently.

Some of the key incentives that shape the conduct of research are the *rewards* that researchers expect to become more probable through lapses in research integrity such as getting a paper published with the help QRP. In academia, desired outcomes such as eminence, job security, promotion, and grant funding are often more or less explicitly contingent on quantitative performance metrics such as publications, citations, and their aggregates such as the H-index (Houle et al., 2023; Simiyu et al., 2021). In some institutions, steps toward these goals are further incentivized with cash-based rewards. This "publish or perish" incentive architecture can reward practices that enhance publication quantity or apparent quality at the expense of research integrity (DuBois et al., 2013; Holtfreter et al., 2020; Wright, 2024). For instance, selectively reporting the results that support one's

hypothesis out of a large and more mixed set of analyses can make a paper seem more coherent and impactful and thereby publishable.

In addition to rewards, incentives also include the *punishments* or negative consequences that are expected to follow an action. The prevalence of low research integrity has been linked to the following factors that limit the probability of adverse consequences. Questionable research practices are difficult to sanction given ongoing debates over their definitions and the complexity of existing rules and regulations (De Jong et al., 2013; Reid et al., 2021). Furthermore, detection of violations depends on co-authors, reviewers, and editors with limited time (Tourish & Craig, 2020). They may also experience conflicting motives as whistleblowers can face legal repercussions in some countries and journals and academic institutions can be concerned with harming institutional reputations (Tourish & Craig, 2020).

In addition to external rewards and punishments, conduct of research is influenced by *internal incentives* such as psychological goals, values and identity (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2019). For instance, researchers motivated by appearance goals (striving to display competence to others) were found more likely to engage in QRPs, while those motivated by learning goals (striving for skill development) were less likely to do so (Janke et al., 2019). Likewise, absence of epistemic virtues (e.g. *honesty* regarding data analysis) and the presence of epistemic vices (e.g. *deception* regarding data fabrication) have been hypothesized as potential precursors to misconduct (Tang, 2024). These findings can be explained by assuming that different actions help people meet their psychological standards (e.g. to appear competent; to be virtuous), thus functioning as expected outcomes of actions that derive subjective value from intrinsic rather than extrinsic rewards and punishments.

1.3.1 Reshaping incentives

The sensitivity of research conduct to incentives opens the door for interventions that seek to re-shape behavior by shaping incentives. The idea of this strategy is to alter the perceived or actual probability or value of expected outcomes of the desired and undesired actions.

Several proposals for facilitating research integrity found in the literature involve re-designing incentives. Some of these are overarching calls for a reform of the broader publish or perish incentive architecture (Moher et al., 2020). For instance, Aubert Bonn and colleagues (2022) proposed (a) restructuring the organization of research to reduce pressure and competition; (b) realigning research assessments to reward quality over quantity; (c) diversifying careers by bridging the gap between academic and non-academic careers, and (d) promoting a shared discussion between all stakeholders with opportunities to build a collective strategy for change. Following the insight that low research integrity often goes unpunished, another broad idea is to clarify and simplify the relevant rules and regulations to increase the probability of punishments.

There are also more specific innovations to the process of scientific communication such as *pre-registration* (Evans et al., 2023; Hardwicke & Wagenmakers, 2023) and registered reports (Chambers & Tzavella, 2022; Scheel et al., 2021). Pre-registration is a time-stamped document

that communicates the hypothesis or other aims of a study alongside the analysis plans ahead of conducting a study. Registered reports are journal papers that are accepted before data collection, based on, in effect, an extended pre-registration. These innovations make specific changes to incentives. Both innovations incentivize thinking through analyses before being able to learn what impact each choice would have on the results. Moreover, pre-registrations make the outcomes of analysis independent from the probability of publication. They also make it costlier to deviate from planned analyses as doing so would complicate the publication process and lower the impact of the findings. There is also some evidence of improved quality, in terms of methodology, analysis, and overall paper quality, of pre-registered reports compared to non-registered ones (Soderberg et al., 2021). Registered reports combine this with uncoupling the publication from results thus removing a disincentive from publishing null findings.

We propose that one relatively understudied area involves facilitating the behavioral impact of intrinsic incentives such as psychological goals, values, and identity, on research integrity. For example, engagement in a QRP such as selective reporting may be reduced by prompts that increase the salience of integrity-related values. Most researchers subscribe to integrity-related values such as honesty and transparency, but at critical decision points these values may lose out to other incentives, including values such as success and status, leading to engagement in QRPs. To a degree, this depends on the salience of different outcomes, or what the researcher is thinking about at a given decision point. This opens the door for cultivating the saliency of integrity values during important decision points. For instance, self-assessment questionnaires presented at paper submission could serve this function. These interventions will probably have small effects, but accumulating over many instances, the outcomes can be worth pursuing. More broadly, interventions should not only establish rules and procedures but also foster and target the activation of relevant values among researchers.

1.3.2 How to get started with reshaping incentives?

Applying the incentive shaping strategy requires identifying the expectations for external and internal rewards and punishments that could be shaped. Here are the questions that could be helpful in this process.

- *Feelings.* Does the desired action make the researcher feel better than the undesirable action? If not, why? How could this be changed?
- *Consequences.* Is the desired action expected to bring more benefits than costs than the undesired action? If not, why? How could this be changed?
- *Identity.* Does the researcher consider the desired action closer to their core values and identity than the undesired action? If not, why? How could this be changed?

Once the key incentives shaping the action of interest have been identified, we can proceed to find ways to shape them. The goal is to come up with interventions that would make researchers think at critical decision points about some of the consequences that they tend to ignore or underappreciate otherwise.

1.4 Communities

Behavior is shaped by various social dynamics within communities. We often follow the lead of others, both specific individuals such as leaders and early adopters as well as perceived norms within the groups we identify with. Think of giving a try to the new social media app everyone is seemingly talking about or not crossing an empty street with a red light when other people are waiting.

Community dynamics are also at play in facilitating and undermining research integrity. The decisions individual researchers make are influenced by what they believe others consider ethically correct or acceptable behaviors. Summaries of studies of research misconduct indeed point to the role of institutional research culture(s) (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2019; Elliott, 2017; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). The climate in research labs (Gan et al., 2024) and research institutions (Brooker & Allum, 2024) can either foster ethical behavior or encourage engagement with QRPs. Decisions are also directly influenced by the actions of others. The “others” here can refer to various types of social agents. This can include people who are close to us in physical or social space. This influence extends to leadership (McIntosh et al., 2020). For instance, psychology doctoral students are more likely to engage in QRPs if their mentors do as well (Swift et al., 2022). For every QRP a mentor committed in Swift et al.’s (2022) study, their students were expected to commit two or more. Social influence can also stem from numbers, the behavior of pluralities and majorities has an impact.

1.4.1 *Reshaping communities*

The sensitivity of research integrity to community dynamics opens the door for interventions that seek to re-shape behavior by shaping communities. The idea of this strategy is to amplify or muffle the social influence of leaders, loud minorities and/or silent majorities.

A rich example is the largely self-organizing “open science movement” that has sought to increase transparency and accessibility of research as a remedy against questionable research practice and outright research misconduct. Many of the innovations the movement has spawned, explicitly or implicitly, can be seen as examples of community shaping. For instance, the movement has reduced the social status of researchers who violate research integrity principles by calling these flaws out. In parallel, it has showcased new open practices, thereby amplifying the social influence of early adopters. It has also devised means such as open science badges to elevate the status of researchers who adhere to them (Kidwell et al., 2016; Rowhani-Farid et al., 2020). The Open Science movement can be considered a large-scale intervention aiming to influence the social norms and expectations surrounding research practices, effectively shaping communities to prioritize and promote research integrity. Similar themes undergird a call to shift the goals of responsible conduct of research training towards building supportive cultures (Kalichman, 2014).

1.4.2 *How to get started with reshaping communities?*

Applying the communities shaping strategy requires identifying the social dynamics that could be shaped. Very often, interventions boil down to changing social perceptions, which can have

a powerful effect on social reality. Here are questions that can help discover opportunities for community shaping.

- *Hidden norm.* Is the desired action practiced more or the undesired action less than is generally believed? If so, how can this be communicated?
- *Pioneers.* Are there early adopters practicing and preaching the desired actions? If so, how to support and broadcast their behavior?
- *Authority.* Is the desired action practiced and preached more than the undesired action by formal or informal leaders of relevant communities? If not, how could that be changed?

Once the key community dynamics shaping the action of interest have been identified, we can proceed to find ways to shape them. The goal is to come up with interventions that would facilitate and broadcast supportive norms, pioneers and authority figures.

1.5 Opportunities

Finally, behavior is shaped by opportunities inherent in situations to act in some way and not in others. We often struggle to complete actions that are difficult, uncomfortable, or tedious, even if we generally value these actions and might have intended to complete them. Think of giving up on filling in a poorly designed survey. Conversely, we can find ourselves doing things that are easy, comfortable, and effortless, even if we did not plan them. Think of exploring a well-designed website for no particular purpose.

The behavioral impact of opportunities is also at play when people conduct research. For instance, if testing for difference between two means is easier, both to think through and to implement in a statistical software, than testing for the equivalence of two means, we tend to misuse absence of a difference as evidence of equivalence.

The impact of opportunities for research integrity is potentially an understudied area. Existing literature points to only a few aspects of the situations where research activities occur as contributors to QRPs. For instance, lack or inaccessibility of support systems such as statistical consulting can threaten research integrity (Davis et al., 2007). We believe there could be other ways in which opportunities influence research integrity. For instance, missing important citations in an introduction can depend on the ease of conducting literature searches. When a database search produces an overwhelming volume of relevant papers, it can be very difficult to identify the key sources, making other strategies such as relying only on a few prior papers more appealing. This suggests that the literature search tools available to researchers may be an important determinant of selective citation. Each QRP may have its own set of such opportunity-level drivers, suggesting there is a need for more work analyzing specific forms of QRPs on the level of specific opportunities in specific situations.

1.5.1 Reshaping opportunities

Shaping the opportunities inherent in the situations where research is conducted constitutes one strategy to facilitate research integrity. The idea of this strategy is to make the desired actions easier to consider and implement relative to the undesired action.

This principle is at the heart of an approach to behavior change referred to as nudging which involves small and often subtle interventions that do not force behavior change but instead guide individuals towards desirable actions by altering the context in which decisions are made. For instance, prompting individuals to articulate the reasoning behind their actions could promote a better epistemic understanding of the consequences of choices at hand. The research integrity field has started to consider nudging, although empirical tests remain rare (Allard & Clavier, 2023).

Such small interventions are inherently contextual, which means they can be developed and validated in a particular setting. We propose that fruitful settings might include statistical software; Word or similar software and file templates; pre-registration portals; publication submission portals; and reviewer worksheets. For instance, to facilitate statistical equivalence testing one could design an R package or SPSS feature that simplifies implementing it, including help for selecting minimal significant differences. Or craft a Word plugin that alerts the author every time they formulate a sentence that uses a high p-value as evidence for equivalence (e.g., “we found that the groups did not differ, $p = 0.44$ ”).

1.5.2 *How to get started with reshaping opportunities?*

Applying the opportunities shaping strategy involves identifying opportunities that matter for a target behavior and that could be feasibly altered. For this purpose, the following questions can be useful. It is advisable to ask such questions separately in relation to specific actions such as *selecting analyses* rather than broad categories such as questionable research practices. Thus, in real world use, the terms “desired action” and “undesired action” can be replaced in each question.

- *Accessibility.* Are the target group members free to act in the desired way, and not to act in an undesirable way? If not, why? How could this be changed?
- *Saliency.* Does the situation make the desired action option come to mind relative to the undesired option? If not, why? How could this be changed?
- *Effort.* Is the desired action easier and more comfortable than the undesired action? If not, why? How could this be changed?

Once the key opportunities shaping the actions of interest have been identified, we can proceed to find ways to alter them. The goal is to craft research situations so that the undesired action options become less accessible, salient, and effortless while desired options become more accessible, salient, and effortless.

2 **Tackling QRPs through Value-Based and Consequence-Based Interventions**

We conducted a large online experiment to investigate the potential impact of two incentive shaping strategies – highlighting internal integrity values and highlighting adverse external consequences at the time of choosing between behavioral options.

We assume that engaging in QRPs involves a series of decisions. Each decision involves competition between available courses of action (e.g. to drop vs to keep analyses with null results) that is resolved by estimation of expected subjective value. This estimation involves evaluating expected outcomes of available course of action in light of relevant motives. The motives can include external rewards and punishments (e.g. to get a paper published; to avoid breaking research rules) as well as internal rewards and punishments such as living up to one's personal values. Finally, we assume that the impact a motive has on the decision depends on its state of psychological activation (i.e., cognitive accessibility).

Relying on these assumptions, we hypothesized that increasing the psychological activation of relevant motives should increase the endorsement of high integrity behaviors. We focused in particular on (a) the motive to live up to personal **values** and (b) on the motive to avoid adverse **consequences**.

In a large online between-subjects experiment ($n = 634$) we asked participants to complete writing assignments designed to selectively increase the psychological activation of a) integrity values; b) negative consequence or c) good writing style as a control condition. All participants completed three structured tasks requiring brief written responses of standardized length (Table 1).

Next, participants read 10 vignettes describing research Integrity dilemmas, evaluated four courses of action and selected the one they would implement (Table 2). One course of action for each vignette represented high integrity behavior while the remaining three represented different low integrity behaviors.

We hypothesized that both value-based and consequence-based conditions will increase the evaluations and endorsement of high integrity decisions.

2.1 Methods

2.1.1 Participants

Participants were recruited from Prolific Academic, a platform allowing researchers to recruit paid volunteers, and compensated for their time at a rate of £9 per hour. We invited participants who had self-reported high proficiency in English and holding or obtaining a PhD. Participants were randomly assigned to one of three experimental conditions. Following pre-registered exclusion criteria, we removed participants who failed two questions designed to detect participants not paying attention to the task. The final sample included 634 participants, evenly distributed throughout the conditions (values $n=214$, consequences $n=211$, control $n=209$).

2.1.2 Design and procedure

Table 1 includes three tasks administered sequentially across all conditions. In Task 1, participants saw different texts on their assigned condition.

- In the **values** condition, participants saw a list of values (Honesty, Respect for others, Accountability, Integrity, Do no harm, Responsibility), selected one, and explained its personal importance in 2-3 sentences.
- In the **consequences** condition, participants saw potential consequences of research integrity violations (Fines, lawsuits, retraction of publications, personal shame, unemployment, damaged reputation), selected one, and explained its personal importance in 2-3 sentences.
- In the control condition, participants saw elements of writing style (Clarity, Convention, Concision, Readability, Precision, Accessibility, Use of examples), selected one, and explained its appeal in 2-3 sentences.

Task 2 was identical across all conditions, asking participants to describe a time in their life that illustrated what they wrote about in Task 1.

The purpose of Task 3 was to prompt participants to reflect on the ways in which behavioral options relate to the motives activated in different conditions. To this end, participants saw the 1st vignette and were asked to analyze it from a perspective that varied between the conditions.

- In the values condition, participants identified which personal value (Honesty, Respect for others, Accountability, Integrity, Do no harm, or Responsibility) was most relevant to the scenario and explained why in 2-3 sentences.
- In the consequences condition, participants selected the most relevant consequence (Fines, lawsuits, retraction of publications, personal shame, unemployment, or damaged reputation) and justified their choice in 2-3 sentences.
- In the control condition, participants identified which element of writing style (Clarity, Convention, Concision, Readability, Precision, Accessibility, or Use of examples) was most relevant to how the scenario text was written and explained their selection in 2-3 sentences.

Next, participants read another 9 vignettes describing dilemmas relevant for research Integrity (see Table 2) and select the best course of action.

Finally, participants reported the following demographic information: Sex; Age; Current country they are working in; Country they received their highest degree; Current (academic) working position; Field of research; Years from the start of higher education in the field; Specialty in the field; Self-reported proficiency in research methods and statistics; How many peer-reviewed publication do you?

Table 1. Writing tasks used in three conditions of the experiment

Values Condition	Punishment condition	Control Condition
Researchers often find themselves navigating dilemmas with no clear	Researchers often find themselves navigating dilemmas with no clear answers. For	Researchers often find themselves navigating dilemmas with no clear

<p>answers. For instance, decisions such as what part of the article to write first and how to present results are often not black and white. Research has shown that often, these situations come down to three core values that many researchers share:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honesty: Telling the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth about everything that went into a study, including methods, results and limitations. • Respect for others: Considering colleagues, research participants, society, and the environment in research conduct and dissemination. • Accountability: Taking responsibility for studies, publications, and wider societal impacts, ensuring transparency and integrity in the research process. 	<p>instance, decisions such as what part of the article to write first and how to present results are often not black and white. Research has shown that scientific misconduct allegations can lead to three devastating consequences for researchers' careers and lives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional ruin: Immediate termination from current positions and long-term unemployability due to damaged reputation in academic circles and media. • Academic erasure: Retraction of publications from journals, often accompanied by public notices detailing the misconduct, erasing years of work. • Legal jeopardy: Facing lawsuits and financial penalties, sometimes amounting to millions in fines, impacting personal life. 	<p>answers. For instance, decisions such as what part of the article to write first and how to present results are often not black and white. Research shows that choosing between passive and active voices in academic writing typically involves three key considerations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity: Using active voice to identify the performer of an action, or passive voice to emphasize the action or result. • Convention: Adhering to disciplinary norms, as some fields favor passive voice for perceived objectivity, while others prefer active voice. • Concision: Selecting the voice that allows for the most precise and economical expression of ideas, avoiding any unnecessary wordiness.
<p>Task 1 A list of values is presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honesty • Respect for others • Accountability • Integrity • Do no harm • Responsibility <p>Choose a value from the list and briefly explain why this value is important for you.</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>	<p>Task 1 A list of consequences is presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fines • Lawsuits • Retraction of publications • Personal shame • Unemployment • Damaged reputation <p>Choose a consequence from the list and briefly explain why this consequence is concerning to you.</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>	<p>Task 1 A list of writing styles is presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity • Convention • Concision • Readability • Precision • Accessibility • Use of examples <p>Choose an element of writing style from the list above and explain why this element of writing style appeals to you.</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>
<p>Task 2</p>	<p>Task 2</p>	<p>Task 2</p>

Describe a time in your life when it has been particularly important. Write 2-3 sentences.	Describe a time in your life when it has been particularly important. Write 2-3 sentences.	Describe a time in your life when it has been particularly important. Write 2-3 sentences.
Task 3 As a first author I have recently submitted a paper to a reputable journal in my field. In the paper I use five different statistical methods to test my hypothesis. Three of these methods give significant results, whereas the other two do not. I can clearly explain these differences between the various methods in my paper. The associate editor emails that he only wants to publish the paper if the two methods that do not give significant results are removed from the paper. What action do I take?		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honesty • Respect for others • Accountability • Integrity • Do no harm • Responsibility <p>Which one of these values is most relevant to this scenario and why?</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fines • Lawsuits • Retraction of publications • Personal shame • Unemployment • Damaged reputation <p>Which one of these consequences is most relevant to this scenario and why?</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity • Convention • Concision • Readability • Precision • Accessibility • Use of examples <p>Which of these elements of style is most relevant to how the text is written?</p> <p>Write 2-3 sentences.</p>

2.1.3 Vignettes

The study measured participants' propensity to act in alignment with research integrity principles using 10 vignettes from the "Dilemma Game Professionalism and Integrity in Research" of Erasmus University Rotterdam. Each vignette described a different situation describing a dilemma (non-significant effects, post-hoc hypothesis, flexible criteria, self-correction, controlling variables, different estimates, reinterpretation, error in analysis, performance data, and grounded conclusions) and participants had to choose one action out of 4 options. Only one option always reflects rejection of research integrity principles (and coded as 0), whereas the other three reflect actions in line (coded as 1). Participants also rated their evaluation of each option on a 7-point Likert-scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree".

Table 2. Vignettes used in the experiment

1. Remove results As a first author I have recently submitted a paper to a reputable journal in my field. In the paper I use five different statistical methods to test my hypothesis. Three of these methods give significant results, whereas the other two do not. I can clearly explain these differences between the various methods in my paper. The associate editor emails that he only wants to publish the
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paper if the two methods that do not give significant results are removed from the paper. What action do I take?

- I agree with the associate editor and remove the two methods.
- I do not agree and email the associate editor asking him to reconsider.
- I inform the editor-in-chief about the comments of the associate editor.
- I cancel the submission and resubmit my paper to another journal.

2. Rewrite

I received a revise and resubmit' decision from a top tier journal. The editor, however, does not like the theoretical framework I used to derive my hypotheses. He suggests a different theoretical framework and asks me to completely re-write the introduction. As a result, my hypotheses would no longer be based on my a priori assumptions, but on a different post-hoc explanation. How do I react?

- I follow the advice of the editor and rewrite the paper.
- I send an email to the editor and explain why I think I should not do this.
- I revise the paper but explain in detail in the revision notes why I disagree with the editor's recommendation.
- I indicate to the editor that I will not resubmit the paper and submit it to another journal.

3. Flexible criteria

A leading senior researcher in my field of interest asks me to work on a project with him. He has already collected the data from fifty randomly selected organizations and I am working on the analysis. After finalizing the paper together and submitting it, a reviewer points out that only thirty organizations meet our sample selection criteria. Making use of a smaller sample threatens the credibility and validity of the results. The senior researcher is not worried at all and tells me to simply change the sample selection criteria so that they are easily met by all fifty organizations. What do I do?

- I accept the change in the sample criteria as proposed by the senior researcher.
- I refrain from changing the sample criteria and withdraw my name from the paper.
- I make sure that the article mentions that the co-author is responsible for the data and methodology.
- I perform an additional survey to come up with 20 new companies that meet our criteria. That will take a significant amount of time and delay the project for a few months.

4. Self-correction

As a researcher I published a new article in a highly prestigious international journal. The article was praised for its thoroughness and scientific breakthrough. While working on an ensuing paper, I realize that I made a mistake in the analysis of the previous paper which has a high impact on the results. What do I do?

- I do nothing.
- I write a correction note paper and send it to the journal.
- I use my current paper to remedy the mistake, but in such a way that no one will notice the mistake in the first paper.
- I discuss the issue with one of my supervisors and follow her advice.

5. Controlling my variables

I am a researcher in a tenure-track position and really need an additional paper to be published. The main hypothesis in the paper I am working on is that A influences B. During the research I

used multiple variables for control purposes. During the analysis it becomes clear that there is no impact of A on B unless I remove one of the control variables. What do I do?

- I remove the variable and do not mention it in my paper.
- I remove the variable and look for scientific arguments for doing so and mention it in the paper.
- I submit my paper without removing the variable even though it might mean that my paper will not be published.
- I ask a peer what she would do. I follow her opinion.

6. Different estimates

I am a PhD student. I have just run a regression analysis, and the results came out nicely. To validate the results, I decide to run two alternative estimation procedures. However, it turns out that the results from the alternative tests are not significantly different from zero, although the point estimates are comparable to the first results. What do I do?

- I only report the results of the first regression analysis.
- I report all results in order to show the robustness of my results.
- I do not report the results but mention in the paper that these strategies yield quantitatively similar conclusions.
- In my discussion I list a number of reasons why performing these additional analyses would be inappropriate.

7. Reinterpretation

I am writing a paper with two colleagues. I am working on the statistical analysis of the data, the first colleague gathered the data, and the second colleague put the theoretical background together and formulated the hypotheses. After the second R&R, I re-read the arguments underlying one of the hypotheses. Some of the underlying articles' meaning has been heavily re-interpreted, to the point that some could argue it has been misrepresented. I am not primarily responsible for the theoretical section, but I am still one of the co-authors. What do I do?

- Keep quiet. If the reviewers and editors have not noticed, the interpretations of the papers given by my colleague in the formulation of my theoretical section might be legitimate.
- I redo the theoretical section myself. As it takes a lot of time, I tell the others I want to be first author.
- I tell my colleague about my different interpretation. If he adheres to his original opinion, I accept this and let it go.
- I discuss the issue with the third colleague directly (the one responsible for data gathering). I feel betrayed by the colleague writing the theoretical section and try to convince my other peer that he should be dropped from the project, even though the research idea was his.

8. So close

After a couple of rounds of reviews, I discover an error/omission in data analysis in a co-authored manuscript. At this point, the paper has almost been accepted, and the reviewers have never made any remark about the data analysis. I know that my co-authors do not want to miss out on the chance to publish. I was not the prime person responsible for this part of the data analysis. What do I do?

- I leave the error/omission in the paper. If the reviewers have not noticed it, then it apparently is not a serious flaw.
- I mention casually to the co-author responsible for this part of the data-analysis that there may be an error, but do not push for re-analysis when she doesn't seem too bothered about it.

- I tell all the co-authors that I cannot take responsibility for the current analysis and tell them to wait with submitting the final version of the manuscript until I have solved it. If they want to go ahead and submit it, I will have my name removed from the paper.
- I inform the lead author of the suspected error, and leave the decision to her, knowing that she needs the publication for her tenure.

9. To perform or not to perform

One of the reviewers of my paper asks whether I can also relate my findings to performance data of the firms I have surveyed. I have collected performance data in my survey, but in the current paper, I have not included any performance data, because my analyses have shown that there are no statistically significant performance effects. How do I respond?

- I say that I do not have any performance data. I include the idea of performance data as a suggestion for future research in my Limitations section.
- I say that I have performance data, but as I do not have any hypotheses on performance in the paper, there is no need to include performance effects in the paper.
- In a separate appendix for the reviewers only, I show my analyses of performance data and try to convince them that these non-significant effects do not add anything to the paper.
- I add analyses of performance effects in the paper and include a discussion of these non-significant effects.

10. Grounded conclusions

Today I had an appointment with one of the directors who funded the research I participated in. While discussing the draft report, it becomes clear that some of the results are not supportive of the director's aims. He requests me to leave out some of the results. He also tells me that by helping him I can be sure of financial support in the future. Our institute depends for more than fifty per cent on this kind of external funding. What do I do?

- I tell him that I will publish the report as it is.
- I agree with the director that some results might be too negative and delete them from the report.
- I do not delete the results completely but leave them out of the executive summary.
- I tell him I will see what I can do. In reality I have no intention in making any real changes

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Treatment effects on choices

We first used a series of 10 logistic regressions to test the condition effects on the odds of selecting the high integrity option in each vignette.

We found that the consequences condition increased the probability of choosing the high integrity option in the first vignette 3.2 times relative to the control condition ($p = .002$). The values condition did not differ significantly from either of the other conditions.

Figure 2. Choice probabilities across conditions and vignettes. Low integrity options are with red outlines. The gray box denotes the vignette with a significant experimental effect.

2.2.2 Treatment effects on evaluations

We used a series of repeated measures ANOVAS to assess the effects of condition on evaluations of each of the four response options. In each model, the mean evaluation rating was predicted from the between-subjects condition factor, within-subjects response option factor and their interaction. Only the interaction term is of substantive interest as this reveals whether the response evaluations were impacted by condition.

We found significant condition effects on ratings in the 1st vignette ($F(6, 1893) = 9.35, p < .001$) and the 7th vignette ($F(6, 1893) = 2.59, p = .017$; see Figure 3). In the 7th vignette, post-hoc pairwise comparisons revealed that only the high integrity option 3 was rated significantly higher in the consequences compared to the control conditions ($b = 0.41, SE = 0.17, p = .048$).

In the 1st vignette, the low integrity option 1 was rated lower both in the consequences condition ($b = -0.97, SE = 0.21, p < .001$) and in the values condition ($b = -0.63, SE = 0.21, p = .008$) compared to the control condition. The consequences and values ratings did not differ ($b = -0.34, SE = 0.21, p = .222$). The high integrity option 2 was rated higher both in the consequences condition ($b = 0.65, SE = 0.19, p = .003$) and the values condition ($b = 0.48, SE = 0.19, p = .037$) compared to the control condition. The consequences and values ratings did not differ ($b = 0.17, SE = 0.19, p = .654$). No significant differences were observed for the high integrity option 3. Finally, the high integrity option 4 was rated higher in the consequences condition ($b = 0.92, SE = 0.18, p < .001$) and lower in the values condition ($b = -0.18, SE = 0.18, p = .006$) compared to the control condition. The consequences and values ratings did not differ ($b = -0.38, SE = 0.18, p = .085$).

Option: ◆ low integrity ◆ high integrity Condition: ○ control ■ consequences ▲ values

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I am a PhD student. I have just run a regression analysis and the results come out nicely. To validate the results I decide to run two alternative estimation procedures. However, it turns out that the results from the alternative tests are not significantly different from zero, although the point estimates are comparable to the first results.

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One of the reviewers of my paper asks whether I can also relate my findings to performance data of the firms I have surveyed. I have collected performance data in my survey, but in the current paper, I have not included any performance data, because my analyses have shown that there are no statistically significant performance effects.

Today I had an appointment with one of the directors who funded the research I participated in. While discussing the draft report, it becomes clear that some of the results are not supportive of the director's aims. He requests me to leave out some of the results. He also tells me that by helping him I can be sure of financial support in the future. Our institute depends for more than fifty per cent on this kind of external funding.

Strongly disagree Disagree Somewhat disagree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat agree Agree Strongly agree Strongly disagree Disagree Somewhat disagree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat agree Agree Strongly agree

Agreement rating (SE)

Figure 3. Evaluations of response options across conditions and vignettes. Low integrity options are in red. The gray box denotes the vignette with a significant experimental effect.

2.2.3 Individual differences

We also analyzed whether the selection of high integrity responses depended on relevant respondent characteristics and whether these characteristics moderated the effects of our manipulations. See Figure 4 for the variables.

Figure 4. Sample characteristics used in the individual difference and moderator analyses

To analyze choices, we conducted 50 logistic regressions, each predicting the odds of selecting the high integrity option in a single vignette from the condition, a single moderator variable and their interaction. We adjusted p-values across the 10 models using a single moderator using the False Discovery Rate algorithm.

We did not find any moderating relationships, suggesting that the effects of the manipulations did not depend on any of the five characteristics.

We also found that **academic field** and self-evaluated **proficiency in research methods** were unrelated to choosing of the high integrity option. The remaining characteristics did impact some choices in the 1st and the 10th vignette. **Research experience:** participants who received their highest degree 10 or more years ago had 2.35 times higher odds of selecting the high integrity option in the first vignette ($p = .001$) and 2.42 higher odds in the 10th vignette ($p = .002$). **Publication record:** Having 8 or more peer-reviewed publications (vs 0 to 3) increased the odds of selecting high integrity responses by 2.19 times ($p = .001$) in the 1st vignette and 2.32 times ($p = .002$) in the 10th vignette. **Academic position:** participants outside

of academia had lower odds of selecting the high integrity option compared to PhD students in the 1st ($OR = 0.26, p < .001$) and in the 10th ($OR = 0.39, p = .020$) vignette.

Individual differences in integrity evaluations revealed a complex pattern of main and moderating effects across experience levels, fields of work, publication history, and proficiency. Experience level interacted significantly with response options, showing that consequence condition has its strongest impact on researchers in the early and middle stages of their careers. This could have important implications for how research integrity training should be tailored to different career stages, with consequence-focused approaches potentially being more effective for those with less experience. Similarly, the field of work produced significant three-way interaction with condition and response option. Social Sciences participants showed the most significant differences between conditions. In both the consequences and values conditions, they rated integrity-rejecting responses significantly higher than those in the control condition, suggesting they may be more sensitive to framing effects. Publication history also moderated the relationship between condition and response option with researchers having more publications (8+) demonstrating more nuanced differentiation across response options. Interestingly, while academic position showed no significant interaction with experimental condition, it did interact with response option suggesting that hierarchical position influences integrity evaluations independent of experimental manipulations.

2.3 Discussion

Our study aimed to investigate the impact of value-based (values condition) and punishment-based (consequences condition) interventions on participants' decision-making and evaluation of integrity-related actions in research. Using 10 vignettes from the Erasmus University Rotterdam's Dilemma Game, we measured both choice selection (whether participants selected the integrity-preserving option) and integrity ratings (participants' evaluations of all response options).

We found that the consequences condition significantly increased the likelihood of selecting the integrity-preserving option compared to the control condition, but only in the first vignette. The values condition did not significantly impact choices, but did reduce evaluation of the low integrity option similarly to the consequences condition.

The condition effects did not depend systematically on most of the 5 participant characteristics that we also analyzed. In an interesting exception, there were some differences in the condition effect on ratings depending on research field.

However, the characteristics on their own were associated with decisions and evaluations. Specifically, the high integrity options were more often selected by participants with 10+ years of experience, researchers with more than 8 publications, and faculty and postdoctoral researchers were. Self-reported research proficiency did not significantly predict integrity-congruent choices.

These results partially confirmed our hypothesis that both value-based and punishment-based interventions would increase the endorsement of decisions representing higher research integrity compared to the control condition. In particular, participants in the values and consequences conditions showed a statistically significant difference compared to the control condition in rejecting behaviour which does not align with research integrity immediately after engaging in reflection and after they were prompted to consider either values or negative consequences in a particular scenario (vignette 1). However, this effect did not generalize to subsequent scenarios where explicit prompting for value reflection or consequence consideration was absent.

These findings align with value affirmation theory and metacognition research, suggesting that when individuals actively engage with their core values or examine potential consequences of research misconduct, and reflect on the implications of their actions - to either their values or personal consequences -, they demonstrate stronger ethical alignment in their decision-making—but crucially, only when these values and consequences remain psychologically salient.

The present study demonstrated that engagement in value-based reflection can support research integrity. Also, our findings demonstrate that manipulation was effective only for the scenario following engagement in reflection and when involving context-specific consideration of either values or negative consequences. This underscores the critical importance of maintaining sustained metacognitive engagement with values or consequences to effectively support ethical decision-making throughout the research process. The implications of this finding are significant for research integrity interventions and training programs. Rather than one-off ethics workshops or value-affirmation exercises, our results suggest that effective interventions should incorporate regular opportunities for researchers to reflect on their values and the consequences of potential misconduct. Additionally, creating research environments that naturally and consistently activate ethical considerations through subtle nudges, visual cues, training, mentorship, and transparent practices may help sustain the psychological accessibility of values that promote research integrity over time. Such ethical nudges could be strategically embedded in research workflows, data analysis software, or manuscript submission systems to trigger value reflection at critical decision points when questionable research practices might otherwise be considered.

3 References

American Association for the Advancement of Science. (2025, February 15). AAAS leaders: We must stay focused amid turmoil. AAAS News. <https://www.aaas.org/news/aaas-leaders-we-must-stay-focused-amid-turmoil>

Albarracín, D., Fayaz-Farkhad, B., & Granados Samayoa, J. A. (2024). Determinants of behaviour and their efficacy as targets of behavioural change interventions. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-024-00305-0>

- Allard, A., & Clavien, C. (2023). Nudging accurate scientific communication. *PLOS ONE*, *18*(8), e0290225.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0290225>
- Antes, A. L., Wang, X., Mumford, M. D., Brown, R. P., Connelly, S., & Devenport, L. D. (2010). Evaluating the Effects That Existing Instruction on Responsible Conduct of Research Has on Ethical Decision Making: *Academic Medicine*, *85*(3), 519–526. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0b013e3181cd1cc5>
- Aubert Bonn, N., De Vries, R. G., & Pinxten, W. (2022). The failure of success: Four lessons learned in five years of research on research integrity and research assessments. *BMC Research Notes*, *15*(1), Article 1.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-022-06191-0>
- Aubert Bonn, N., & Pinxten, W. (2019). A Decade of Empirical Research on Research Integrity: What Have We (Not) Looked At? *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, *14*(4), 338–352.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264619858534>
- Benartzi, S., Beshears, J., Milkman, K. L., Sunstein, C. R., Thaler, R. H., Shankar, M., Tucker-Ray, W., Congdon, W. J., & Galing, S. (2017). Should Governments Invest More in Nudging? *Psychological Science*, *28*(8), 1041–1055.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797617702501>
- Brooker, R., & Allum, N. (2024). Investigating the links between questionable research practices, scientific norms and organisational culture. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, *9*(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-024-00151-x>
- Brummel, B. J., Gunsalus, C. K., Anderson, K. L., & Loui, M. C. (2010). Development of Role-Play Scenarios for Teaching Responsible Conduct of Research. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, *16*(3), 573–589.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-010-9221-7>
- Chambers, C. D., & Tzavella, L. (2022). The past, present and future of Registered Reports. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *6*(1), 29–42.
- Davis, M. S., Riske-Morris, M., & Diaz, S. R. (2007). Causal Factors Implicated in Research Misconduct: Evidence from ORI Case Files. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, *13*(4), 395–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-007-9045-2>
- De Jong, J. P., Van Zwieten, M. C. B., & Willems, D. L. (2013). Research monitoring by US medical institutions to protect human subjects: Compliance or quality improvement? *Journal of Medical Ethics*, *39*(4), 236–241.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2011-100434>

- DuBois, J. M., Anderson, E. E., Chibnall, J., Carroll, K., Gibb, T., Ogbuka, C., & Rubbelke, T. (2013). Understanding Research Misconduct: A Comparative Analysis of 120 Cases of Professional Wrongdoing. *Accountability in Research*, 20(5–6), 320–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2013.822248>
- Elliott, C. (2017). Institutional Pathology and the Death of Dan Markingson. *Accountability in Research*, 24(2), 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2016.1246969>
- Evans, T. R., Branney, P., Clements, A., & Hatton, E. (2023). Improving evidence-based practice through preregistration of applied research: Barriers and recommendations. *Accountability in Research*, 30(2), 88–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2021.1969233>
- Fanelli, D. (2011). The black, the white and the grey areas: Towards an international and interdisciplinary definition of scientific misconduct. In T. Meyer & N. H. Steneck (Eds.), *Promoting research integrity in a global environment* (pp. 79–90). World Scientific Publishing.
- Fink, M., Gartner, J., Harms, R., & Hatak, I. (2023). Ethical Orientation and Research Misconduct Among Business Researchers Under the Condition of Autonomy and Competition. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 183(2), 619–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05043-y>
- Frazier, L. D., Schwartz, B. L., & Metcalfe, J. (2021). The MAPS model of self-regulation: Integrating metacognition, agency, and possible selves. *Metacognition and Learning*, 16(2), 297–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-020-09255-3>
- Gan, Y., Shi, Y., & Wang, G. (2024). Publication pressure and questionable research practices: A moderated mediation model. *Ethics & Behavior*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2024.2397103>
- Gopalakrishna, G., ter Riet, G., Vink, G., Stoop, I., Wicherts, J. M., & Bouter, L. M. (2022). Prevalence of questionable research practices, research misconduct and their potential explanatory factors: A survey among academic researchers in The Netherlands. *PLOS ONE*, 17(2), e0263023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0263023>
- Hale, J., Hastings, J., West, R., Lefevre, C. E., Direito, A., Bohlen, L. C., Godinho, C., Anderson, N., Zink, S., Groarke, H., & Michie, S. (2020). An ontology-based modelling system (OBMS) for representing behaviour change theories applied to 76 theories. *Wellcome Open Research*, 5, 177. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16121.1>

- Hardwicke, T. E., & Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2023). Reducing bias, increasing transparency and calibrating confidence with preregistration. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 7(1), 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01497-2>
- Holtfreter, K., Reisig, M. D., Pratt, T. C., & Mays, R. D. (2020). The perceived causes of research misconduct among faculty members in the natural, social, and applied sciences. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(11), 2162–2174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1593352>
- Iordanou, K. (2022). Supporting strategic and meta-strategic development of argument skill: The role of reflection. *Metacognition and Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-021-09289-1>
- Janke, S., Daumiller, M., & Rudert, S. C. (2019). Dark Pathways to Achievement in Science: Researchers' Achievement Goals Predict Engagement in Questionable Research Practices. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 10(6), 783–791. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550618790227>
- Kalichman, M. (2014). Rescuing Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) Education. *Accountability in Research*, 21(1), 68–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2013.822271>
- Kidwell, M. C., Lazarević, L. B., Baranski, E., Hardwicke, T. E., Piechowski, S., Falkenberg, L.-S., Kennett, C., Slowik, A., Sonnleitner, C., & Hess-Holden, C. (2016). Badges to acknowledge open practices: A simple, low-cost, effective method for increasing transparency. *PLoS Biology*, 14(5), e1002456.
- Labib, K., Evans, N., Roje, R., Kavouras, P., Reyes Elizondo, A., Kaltenbrunner, W., Buljan, I., Ravn, T., Widdershoven, G., & Bouter, L. (2022). Education and training policies for research integrity: Insights from a focus group study. *Science and Public Policy*, 49(2), 246–266.
- Marušić, A. (2023). Evidence-based research integrity. In *Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice: The ETHNA System Project* (pp. 173–187). Springer.
- McIntosh, T., Sanders, C., & Antes, A. L. (2020). Leading the people and leading the work: Practical considerations for ethical research. *Translational Issues in Psychological Science*, 6(3), 257–270. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tps0000260>
- Moher, D., Bouter, L., Kleinert, S., Glasziou, P., Sham, M. H., Barbour, V., Coriat, A.-M., Foeger, N., & Dirnagl, U. (2020). The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity. *PLOS Biology*, 18(7), e3000737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>

- Powell, S. T., Allison, M. A., & Kalichman, M. W. (2007). Effectiveness of a responsible conduct of research course: A preliminary study. *Science and Engineering Ethics, 13*(2), 249–264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-007-9012-y>
- Reid, C., Calia, C., Guerra, C., Grant, L., Anderson, M., Chibwana, K., Kawale, P., & Amos, A. (2021). Ethics in global research: Creating a toolkit to support integrity and ethical action throughout the research journey. *Research Ethics, 17*(3), 359–374. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016121997522>
- Rowhani-Farid, A., Aldcroft, A., & Barnett, A. G. (2020). Did awarding badges increase data sharing in BMJ Open? A randomized controlled trial. *Royal Society Open Science, 7*(3), 191818.
- Scheel, A. M., Schijen, M. R., & Lakens, D. (2021). An excess of positive results: Comparing the standard psychology literature with registered reports. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science, 4*(2), 25152459211007467.
- Sivasubramaniam, S. D., Khan, Z. R., & Razi, S. (2022). Understanding the Enablers and Barriers of Ethical Guidance and Review for Academic Research. In S. Bjelobaba, T. Foltýnek, I. Glendinning, V. Krásničan, & D. H. Dlabolová (Eds.), *Academic Integrity: Broadening Practices, Technologies, and the Role of Students* (Vol. 4, pp. 17–28). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16976-2_2
- Soderberg, C. K., Errington, T. M., Schiavone, S. R., Bottesini, J., Thorn, F. S., Vazire, S., Esterling, K. M., & Nosek, B. A. (2021). Initial evidence of research quality of registered reports compared with the standard publishing model. *Nature Human Behaviour, 5*(8), 990–997. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01142-4>
- Swift, J. K., Christopherson, C. D., Bird, M. O., Zöld, A., & Goode, J. (2022). Questionable research practices among faculty and students in APA-accredited clinical and counseling psychology doctoral programs. *Training and Education in Professional Psychology, 16*(3), 299–305. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tep0000322>
- Tang, B. L. (2024). Deficient epistemic virtues and prevalence of epistemic vices as precursors to transgressions in research misconduct. *Research Ethics, 20*(2), 272–287. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17470161231221258>
- Tijdink, J. K., Bouter, L. M., Veldkamp, C. L. S., Van De Ven, P. M., Wicherts, J. M., & Smulders, Y. M. (2016). Personality Traits Are Associated with Research Misbehavior in Dutch Scientists: A Cross-Sectional Study. *PLOS ONE, 11*(9), e0163251. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0163251>

- Tourish, D., & Craig, R. (2020). Research Misconduct in Business and Management Studies: Causes, Consequences, and Possible Remedies. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 29(2), 174–187.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1056492618792621>
- Vazire, S. (2024). The Next Chapter for Psychological Science. *Psychological Science*, 35(7), 703–707.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09567976231221558>
- Watts, L. L., Medeiros, K. E., Mulhearn, T. J., Steele, L. M., Connelly, S., & Mumford, M. D. (2017). Are Ethics Training Programs Improving? A Meta-Analytic Review of Past and Present Ethics Instruction in the Sciences. *Ethics & Behavior*, 27(5), 351–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2016.1182025>
- West, R., Godinho, C. A., Bohlen, L. C., Carey, R. N., Hastings, J., Lefevre, C. E., & Michie, S. (2019). Development of a formal system for representing behaviour-change theories. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 3(5), Article 5.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0561-2>
- Wright, D. E. (2024). Five problems plaguing publishing in the life sciences—And one common cause. *FEBS Letters*, 598(18), 2227–2239. <https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.15018>
- Xie, Y., Wang, K., & Kong, Y. (2021). Prevalence of Research Misconduct and Questionable Research Practices: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 27(4), 41.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00314-9>